

Electrochemical Behaviour of some (*N*-Bromo-*N*-phenylhydrazono)-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-diones

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N-Bromo-*N*-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1, 3-diones have been studied over a wide pH range at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrodes. These compounds give one four-electron wave corresponding to the reduction of hydrazono group and one two-electron wave corresponding to the cleavage of C-NH₂ bond. On the basis of polarography, linear and cyclic sweep voltammetry, coulometry, ir, mass and nmr spectral studies and product identification, a mechanism has been postulated for the reduction process.

Monoarylhrazones of β -diketones are important starting materials for the synthesis of compounds of biological importance¹ and also well-known as powerful chelating agents². The presence of bromine in these compounds makes them effective antifungal and antibacterial agents³. The polarographic behaviour of hydrazono compounds has been the subject matter of many investigations⁴. Four-electron reduction is usually observed in acidic solutions⁵ involving the cleavage of -N-N- bond during reduction. Four-electron reduction of hydrazones has been reported⁶ in acidic medium as well as in alkaline media with the formation of amino compounds. However, Fahmy *et al.*⁷ reported further reduction of α -aminoketone to ammonia and a ketone in two-electron wave. A survey of literature reveals that the redox behaviour of brominated hydrazones has not been critically examined. The present paper summarises the results of electrochemical reduction of *N*-bromo-*N*-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione :

Results and Discussion

Polarographic studies : All the bromo compounds (Table 1) exhibited one four-electron polarographic reduction wave in the pH range 2.0–6.0. This wave was assigned to the reduction of hydrazono group on the basis of number of electrons involved. The values of half-wave potentials and wave-heights of the bromo derivatives were comparable with that of 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione which does not bear a bromo group but having hydrazono group under similar experimental conditions. This confirms that the wave was due to the reduction of hydrazono group. The limiting current of this wave was found to be diffusion-controlled⁸ on the basis of linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ and i_d vs concn. and low values ($\sim 1.6\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$) of temperature coefficient. The shift of half-wave potential towards more negative potentials with concentration of depolariser and logarithmic analysis confirmed the irreversible nature⁸ of the electrode process. The half-wave potential of the four-electron reduction peak shifted to more negative potentials with rise in pH. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is straight-line upto pH ~ 7.8 , whereas at higher pH, the values of $E_{1/2}$ becomes practically constant.

At higher pH values, (pH > 6.0) one more two-electron

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF *N*-BROMO-*N*-PHENYLHRAZONO-1-PHENYLAMINOBTAN-1,3-DIONES

Sl. no.	R	M.p. ^a	$-(E_{1/2})_1^b$ V	$-(E_{1/2})_2^c$ V	$(i_d)_1^b$ μA	$(i_d)_2^c$ μA	I	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ V/pH	α_n	K_{th}^0 cm s^{-1}
1.	H	202	0.82	1.33	0.88	0.35	0.52	0.066	1.27	3.1×10^{-6}
2.	2-CH ₃	152	0.84	1.31	0.75	0.40	0.49	0.067	1.15	9.2×10^{-6}
3.	3-CH ₃	177	0.84	1.30	0.75	0.40	0.49	0.066	1.23	6.2×10^{-6}
4.	4-CH ₃	160	0.86	1.33	0.80	0.40	0.52	0.062	1.23	4.5×10^{-6}
5.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	205	0.83	1.33	0.75	0.35	0.49	0.060	1.27	1.1×10^{-7}
6.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	196	0.84	1.31	0.75	0.34	0.49	0.060	1.23	9.7×10^{-6}
7.	4-C ₂ H ₅	138	0.86	1.35	0.70	0.35	0.46	0.066	1.15	9.2×10^{-6}
8.	4-C ₄ H ₉	130	0.87	1.32	0.75	0.40	0.49	0.077	1.23	3.1×10^{-6}
9.	4-C ₅ H ₁₁	120	0.89	1.33	0.70	0.35	0.46	0.067	1.23	9.2×10^{-6}
10.	4-C ₆ H ₁₃	135	0.90	1.30	0.70	0.30	0.46	0.067	1.27	6.2×10^{-6}
11.	4-C ₇ H ₁₅	132	0.92	1.35	0.70	0.30	0.46	0.067	1.23	6.2×10^{-6}

^aM.p. uncorrected. ^bFor the reduction of hydrazono group. ^cFor the reduction of activated C-N bond.

wave started appearing at more negative potentials which has been assigned to the reduction of α -aminoketone formed at four-electron stage. Reduction of the C-N bond has been reported by other workers also⁹. Both the height and half-wave potential of this wave are pH-independent and the wave is irreversible. The reduction of C-N bond is confirmed by controlled potential electrolysis. One of the products on gas chromatographic analysis was identified as acetoacetanilide. The solution after controlled potential

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PEAK POTENTIAL (E_p , V) AND PEAK CURRENT (i_p , μ A) FOR THE REDUCTION OF *N*-BROMO-*N*-PHENYLHYDRAZONO-1-PHENYLAMINOBUTAN-1,3-DIONES

pH = 6.5, concn. = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

S. no ^a	$-(E_p)_1$ V	$-(E_p)_2$ V	$-(i_p)$ μ A	$-(i_p)_2$ μ A
1.	0.85	1.50	4.4	2.50
2.	0.86	1.48	4.0	2.20
3.	0.86	1.50	5.2	2.00
4.	0.89	1.52	4.4	2.00
5.	0.85	1.50	3.5	1.52
6.	0.84	1.50	3.8	1.60
7.	0.90	1.48	4.2	2.00
8.	0.91	1.48	3.4	1.50
9.	0.91	1.52	3.0	1.40
10.	0.93	1.50	3.2	1.50
11.	0.94	1.50	3.0	1.50

*Compounds as in sl. no. of Table 1.

electrolysis also gave positive test for ammonia by Nessler's reagent¹⁰. The formation of NH_3 probably results from the reduction of the protonated form.

Linear sweep and cyclic voltammetry : Cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 1) of bromo compounds (Table 2) recorded

Fig. 1. Typical cyclic voltammograms of *N*-bromo-*N*-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane at (i) pH 4.0, concn. $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, (ii) pH 2.4, 1.0×10^{-4} and (iii) pH 2.5, $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

at different scan rates and concentrations using glassy carbon electrode exhibited well-defined cathodic peak in the range 2.0–6.0. This behaviour is in agreement with that observed from polarographic measurements. The linear plots of peak current i_p vs the square-root of sweep rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) and i_p vs concentration show little deviation from the origin indicating that electrode reaction is mainly diffusion-controlled¹¹. Peak potentials shifted towards negative potential with pH upto pH ~ 7.5 and thereafter no shift in E_p was observed. On reversing the scan, no anodic peak was observed.

At pH > 6.0 , the bromo compound gave two peaks (Table 2), the first peak being irreversible, diffusion-controlled which shifted towards negative potential with pH, whereas the second peak was pH-independent. The first peak has been assigned to the reduction of the hydrazono group and the second one to the irreversible reduction of the N-C bond as in the case at dropping mercury electrode.

Coulometry and product analysis : The values of n and products determined at different pH values and at different potentials are summarised in Table 3. The four-electron electrolysis at -1.0 V at pH 4.0 yielded two compounds

TABLE 3—VALUES OF n DETERMINED BY COULOMETRY AND COMPOSITION OF PRODUCTS IN CONTROLLED POTENTIAL ELECTROLYSIS OF *N*-BROMOPHENYLHYDRAZONO-1-PHENYLAMINOBUTAN-1,3-DIONES AT A GLASSY CARBON ELECTRODE

Sl no	pH	E V	n	Products (obtained after c.p.c.)
1.	4.0	-1.00	4.20	Brominated aromatic amine (I), aminoketone (II)
		-1.60	4.15	Brominated aromatic amine (I), aminoketone (II)
2.	6.5	-1.00	4.10	Brominated aromatic amine (I), aminoketone (II)
		-1.60	6.20	Brominated aromatic amine (I), 1-aminophenylbutan-1,3-diones (II), ammonia (III)
3.	8.5	-1.60	6.25	Brominated aromatic amine (I), 1-aminophenylbutan-1,3-diones (II), ammonia (III)
4.	10.5	-1.60	6.20	Brominated aromatic amine (I), 1-aminophenylbutan-1,3-diones (II), ammonia (III)

with $R_f \sim 0.32$ and 0.58. One of these compounds may be the brominated aromatic amine (I). The other compound was identified as (II) : ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 220 (NH_2), 2 650 (CH), 1 645 cm^{-1} ($COCH_3$); δ 1.7 (1H, CH), 2.6 (3H, CH_3), 3.8 (2H, NH_2), 7.2–8.0 (2H, ArH). Controlled potential electrolysis at pHs 6.5, 8.5 and 10.5 at -1.6 V and subsequent electrolysis confirmed the presence of brominated aromatic amine (I), 1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones (II) and NH_3 (III).

Redox mechanism : On the basis of DCP, LSV and CPE

the following mechanism may be proposed for bromo compounds :

At pH > 6.0, a similar mechanism has been postulated :

On the basis of these mechanistic studies and the number of electrons involved in the reduction and the nature of reduction products, the structures of these compounds clearly point towards a hydrazono structure.

Effect of substituents : As in this reaction series the value of transfer coefficient⁸ (α_n) and $dE_{1/2}/dpH$ (Table 1) are reasonably constant. Conditions of applying the Hammett equation are thus fulfilled. In order to express the effect of substituents quantitatively the half-wave potentials of all these compounds were plotted against Hammett substituent constant values of σ_{o-x} were taken from literature. A linear relationship between the half-wave potentials and Hammett substituent constant (σ) have been obtained. It is found that all the derivatives except 2-CH₃, 2,3-(CH₃)₂, 2,5-(CH₃)₂ fit in the regression line and the value of the specific reaction constant is 0.19 V. As in this series half-wave potential of *ortho*-derivative is available, viz. 2-CH₃, the corrected half-wave potential for the steric effect for this compound is calculated using the expression,

$$(E_{1/2})_{\text{corrected}} = [E_{1/2} - \delta_{\pi,R}(E_S)_{o-x}]$$

where

$$\delta_{\pi,R} = \frac{(E_S)_{o-x}}{E_{1/2} - \delta_{\pi,R}\sigma_{o-x}}$$

Values of steric substituent constant (E_S)_{o-x} was taken from the literature. The corrected value of half-wave potentials for derivative so obtained is further plotted along with *meta*- and *para*-derivatives and now all the derivatives, except disubstituted, fit in the regression line (Fig. 2). The value of the specific reaction constant (ρ) for the corrected plot was found to be 0.18 V as against 0.19 V. Similar values of ρ has also been reported by other work-

Fig. 2. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs σ of *N*-bromo-*N*-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-diones: concn. = 1.0×10^{-4} M, pH = 6.5

ers for similar systems. The positive values of ρ further suggest a nucleophilic mechanism for the electrode process.

Experimental

Copper chelates of 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-diones : An aqueous solution of copper acetate (0.0025 mol) was added to an alcoholic solution of hydrazono compound (0.005 mol). The pH of the solution was adjusted in the range of 7–8 by adding liq. ammonia dropwise. With stirring green crystals of copper chelates were obtained, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol, (58%), m.p. 215°.

***N*-Bromo-*N*-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione :** Bromine (4.00×10^{-3} mol) in dry CCl₄ (4.0 ml) was added to a solution of the copper chelate of 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-diones (0.002 mol) in dry CCl₄ (15 ml). The precipitate, CuBr₂ was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised from ethanol to give needles of yellow crystals, m.p. 202° (Found : C, 54.67; H, 3.91; N, 12.11. C₁₆H₁₄O₂N₃Br requires : C, 54.85; H, 4.00; N, 12.00%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 680, 1 590, 1 320, 750 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 7.4 (10H, 2-phenyl), 2.4 (3H, CH₃).

Stock solutions of all these bromo derivatives were prepared in DMF. BR buffers¹² in pH range 2.5–12.0 were prepared. An Elico DC CL-25 polarograph was used with capillary characteristics : $m = 2.92$ mg s⁻¹; $t = 4.0$ s; $h = 60$ cm. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. Temperature coefficient was determined by Nejdley method. Cyclic voltammetric Studies were carried out on a BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph. A three-electrode cell system with glassy carbon as working, Ag/AgCl

in 1.0 M NaCl as reference electrode and Pt-wire as counter-electrode was used. Polarograms and voltammograms of solutions containing the stock solution (1.0 ml), DMF (2.5 ml), appropriate buffer (5 ml) and tetraethylammonium bromide (1.0 M, 1.0 ml) as supporting electrolyte were recorded.

For coulometric determination¹³ of number of electrons involved in the electrode process, an aliquot (3.0 ml) of a solution of containing buffer and supporting electrolyte (in the same ratio as used in the typical polarographic experiment) was electrolysed at the plateau potential of the wave. Progress of the electrolysis was monitored by recording the polarograms at different time intervals. Preparative electrolysis was carried out in solutions (5.0 ml) at a concentration of $10^{-3}M$ at DME keeping a blanket of nitrogen over the surface of the solution. The products of electrolysis were identified by comparison of their properties with the expected products using an Amil Nucon 5700 gas liquid chromatograph.

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